

A STUDY ON STRESS MANAGEMENT AMONG WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY

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Abstract:

Stress is defined as "a state of psychological and physiological imbalance resulting from the disparity between situational demand and the individual's ability and motivation to meet those needs." Stress has often been misunderstood to be negative, with few people acknowledgement the importance and usefulness of positive stress. The main objective is to find out the level of stress among the employees of different age groups and to identify the effective dimension of stress among employees. For this a sample of 70 was collected from the employees of Jenntex were t-test, Anova, percentage analysis and mean scores are used as tools to analyse the data and the conclusion is that level of acceptance towards withdrawal has an influence towards the age of the respondents and age has to be taken in to consideration for the decision making process when taking decision on the factors related to level of acceptance towards withdrawal with the respondents and while taking decision on level of acceptance towards work performance the factors related to Perception towards Psychological symptoms has to be taken for decision making process of the study.

Key words: Stress, motivation and withdrawal

Statement of the Problem: Stress is one of the most important things that play a major role in human life. Since all the companies depend upon man power, it is one of the important issues to be taken care of and also it has become a major concern of the modern times. Stress can cause harm to employee's health and performance. Work related stress may lead to sickness, high turnover and high absenteeism. Job stress is a condition arising from the interaction of people that force deviate from their timing. So it becomes necessary for every organization to know about the level of stress among the employees and its consequences so that the company can overcome it.

Objective of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the level of stress among the women employees of different age groups.
- ✓ To identify the factors causing stress among the women employees.
- ✓ To study about the coping strategies to manage stress.
- ✓ To identify the effective dimension of stress among women employees.
- ✓ To offer suitable suggestion on the basis of findings of the study.

Need for the Study: Research on stress is of great relevance to modern society as it provides a new dimension to the understanding and dealing of social problems. The social psychological approach to the problem of stress has widened the scope of stress research as it calls for the study of social institutions and situations from which the stressor variables originate. A substantial number of studies have been reported about stress under normal as well as isolated work environment. The results of these studies have revealed that certain occupations are more stressful than others. A review of occupational stress research clearly reveals that most of the research in this area has concentrated only on industrial and commercial organizations especially under normal work environment. Stress is becoming a global phenomenon affecting all professions and all categories of employees. It is often assumed that employees of information technology because of their nature of work are more vulnerable than other professionals to the ravages of stress. Stress is one of the most deliberating personal and medical problems of modern complex organizations. Challenges posed by the changing business scenario are forcing information technology employees to perform their task under a very compelling situation. The need of the study is that as the employees have stress towards their work based on different reasons it has to be minimized to reduce the stress in future period of time.

Scope of Study:

- ✓ Stress will badly affect the employees both at work place and in personal life. If stress is managed properly.
- ✓ It is beneficial to employees as well as the organization in terms of production, improved relationships both on and off the job. Also it leads to better teamwork and communication.
- ✓ The employee's turnover will be low and the absenteeism rate will be lower. Also the retention of valued employees is possible.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The sample size is limited to 150 as the employees of the companies are limited to 150.

- ✓ There is a bias with the collection of data as the respondents may wrong answers for the questions asked to them.
- ✓ The study time is limited to 3 months so a deep analysis about the research cannot be found.

Conceptual Frame Work:

Research Methodology:

Sampling Techniques: Sampling unit can be defined as the basic unit containing the stress towards Jenntex.

Sampling Size: In this research, the sample size amount to one hundred and fifty, which are surveyed from women employees of the textile industry.

Sampling Type: Convenience sampling I adapted in this research. It is a non-probability sampling and it is refers to selecting a sample based on convenience.

Data Collection: The primary data the respondents which or collected with a questionnaire schedule was used with women employees of the textile industry.

Secondary data were collected from the company profile, manuals, journals, magazines and newspapers etc.

Research Tool: Structures self administered questionnaire had been used as a research tool for collecting

Tools Used for the Study	Attributes of the Study
Percentage Analysis	Demographic profile of the respondents
Mean Score Value	Work performance of the employees Withdrawal of the employees Regression of the employees Aggressive behavior of the employees Psychological symptoms of the employees Behavioral symptoms of the employees Physical symptoms of the employees
Paired Sample T-Test	Comparison between level of acceptance towards work performance and various symptoms of stress
One Way Anova	Relationship between age and factors related to stress

Mean Score Value: The mean score value of the factors related to stress are calculated. The stress level of the employee is been segregated in to signs of stress and dimensions of stress. The signs of stress is been segregated in to work performance, withdrawal, regression and aggressive behavior where as dimensions of stress is been segregated in to psychological symptoms, behavioral symptoms, and physical symptoms.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Age:

	Frequency	Percent
18-25	41	58.6
26-30	29	41.4
Total	70	100.0

Major number of respondents belongs to the category between 18-25 where they would have initial experience towards their job description. According to C. Balakrishnamurthy and Swetha Shankar (2009), age has a strong relationship towards stress level of the employees.

Mean Scores Related to Work Performance of the Employees: It discusses about the mean scores related to work performance of the employees were the average mean value for the factors related to level of acceptance towards work performance of the employees is at 3.

S.No	Particulars	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean
Work Performance							
1	Declining/inconsistent performance	8	15	38	9	0	2.69
2	Uncharacteristic	7	26	16	16	5	2.80
3	Loss of control over work	13	27	20	5	5	2.46
4	Loss of motivation/communication	11	8	13	16	22	3.43
5	Increased time at work	32	15	10	13	0	3.06

Interpretation: The mean value of acceptance towards loss of motivation and communication (3.43) and acceptance towards increased time at work (3.06) are higher than 3. It shows that the employees are not accepting for the factors and remedy measures has to be taken for the factors related to the above said factors. As an employer, it is important to look at things from the employee's perspective and realize that they are most likely not in the same place you are, whether professionally, financially, or even personally. It is important to be able to empathize with the employees. Get up and moving—don't sit in a desk job for more than an hour at a time

Paired Sample T-Test:

		t	df	Sig. (2-Tailed)
H01	Level of acceptance towards work performance - Perception towards Psychological symptoms	-2.793	149	.006
H02	Level of acceptance towards Aggressive behavior - Perception towards Behavioral symptoms	-3.036	148	.003
H03	Level of acceptance towards Regression - Perception towards Physical symptoms	-1.937	149	.055

Interpretation: The above table with part 1 shows about the relationship between level of acceptance towards work performance and perception towards Psychological symptoms were the level of significance is at 0.006 which is lesser than 0.05. It shows that there is a relationship between level of acceptance towards work performance and perception towards Psychological symptoms.

One Way Anova:

Relationship Between Age and Factors Related to Stress:

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig
Level of acceptance towards work performance	18-25	41	2.9366	.71476	.382	.539
	26-30	29	2.8138	.94858		
	Total	70	2.8857	.81548		
Level of acceptance towards withdrawal	18-25	41	2.9268	.72492	4.326	.041
	26-30	29	2.5793	.63323		
	Total	70	2.7829	.70505		

Interpretation: The above table shows about the relationship between age and factors related to stress were there is a relationship between age and level of acceptance towards withdrawal as the level of significance is less than 0.05.

Findings:

Suggestions:

As an employer, it is important to look at things from the employee's perspective and realize that they are most likely not in the same place you are, whether professionally, financially, or even personally. It is important to be able to empathize with the employees. Get up and moving—don't sit in a desk job for more than an hour at a time

- The company can arrange for aerobic exercise activity that raises their heart rate and makes them sweat is a hugely effective way to lift their mood, increase energy, sharpen focus, and relax both the mind and body.

The company can empower staff to control their own workload and consider whether it is appropriate to provide additional support for staff during periods of change and uncertainty.

- The firm can ensure that the demands placed on employees while at work are reasonable. This is not confined to the pure job the person does, but the role they have at work, from when they enter the workplace to when they leave.
- The health and safety executive says around 9.9 million working days are lost each year to stress, depression or anxiety. For this the company has give more stress relief programs to the employees of the company.

REDUTION IN STRESS LEVEL

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that Level of acceptance towards withdrawal has an influence towards the age of the respondents and age has to be taken in to consideration for the decision making process when taking decision on the factors related to level of acceptance towards withdrawal with the respondents and while taking decision on Level of acceptance towards work performance the factors related to Perception towards Psychological symptoms has to be taken for decision making process of the study.

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